

Transformational change of regional landscapes: Navigating planetary limits and resource constraints over the next five decades

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Project Objectives

Current trajectories of resource use and environmental degradation will result in widespread and significant change to communities and landscapes in the coming five decades. Avoiding crisis and cultivating prosperity within the natural limits of our world requires us to rethink the traditional differentiation of land for agricultural production and land for biodiversity conservation. It also requires a shift in perspective to recognize that our current landscapes have evolved rapidly in a time of resource and energy abundance. As a result, development has pushed a number of critical measures beyond safe limits, including greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity loss and nitrogen extracted from the atmosphere for human use. Continued development will also have to contend with the depletion of, and associated price increases in, fossil fuels and fertilizers.

The project brought together a group of Australian researchers and managers with a broad range of expertise to identify current and emerging economies ('drivers') affecting regional agricultural landscapes and to suggest beneficial transformational changes for successful adaptation. A key challenge in these landscapes is altering how we use the land for ongoing, viable production while increasing native biodiversity. To make progress we needed insights from people familiar with the social-ecological system that is a regional landscape. Two questions were posed:

- Is it possible to transform an existing agricultural landscape to overcome the current degradation trends and impending production and conservation limits?
- If so, what biophysical, social, institutional, business, economic and political components are needed in an integrated process design and action framework that has a good chance of achieving transformational change?

The intention was to produce an authoritative science-based report to inspire the Australian government to develop a policy white paper on navigating transformational change in regional landscapes over the next five decades.

Methods

A single, five day workshop was convened. A facilitated process refined the purpose of the project and outlined a structure that assembled the information, guided analysis, and drew up recommendations. The group:

- identified the major historical influences on Australian land use and the current social and economic drivers that are likely to increase in the future.
- assessed the condition of five agro-climatic regions (adapted from Williams et al. 2002 and Hobbs and McIntyre 2005) using a Delphi method. A small (4-person) expert panel scored the impact of historical and future scenarios on ten sustainability indicators (biodiversity, water, soil, social capital, built capital, food/fibre, carbon, energy, minerals and cultural). Five regions were chosen: Southern Mediterranean, Northern tropical, Central arid, North-east subtropical, and South-east temperate (Figure 1). This was an iterative process whereby scores were revisited until internal consistency between regions, scenarios, and indicators was achieved.
- made projections of regional condition under the four global Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) based on van Vuuren et al. (2011) (Appendix 1).
- developed recommendations about land use and management, institutional and policy arrangements and social processes that will assist adaptation towards a values-rich vision of Australia in 2100.

Figure 1: Five agro-climatic regions of Australia adapted from Williams et al. (2002) and Hobbs and McIntyre (2005).

Participants Institutions

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Major Findings

The evidence that we have changed the agro-climatic regions of Australia is compelling (Figure 2). The most obvious changes from European settlement (1788) to current day (2011), are summarised as follows:

- Three regions, Southern Mediterranean, South-east temperate and North-east sub-tropical, have undergone the greatest change; and
- Two regions, Northern tropical and Central arid, have undergone the least change.

Figure 2: Direction and magnitude of historical changes in sustainability indicators for the five agro-climatic regions of Australia following European settlement (1788) to current day (2011). The scale: 0 was the indicator score in 1788. +1 indicates a maximum positive change and -1, a maximum negative change as at 2011.

As with historic change, future risks and opportunities differ between regions (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Direction and magnitude of future changes in sustainability indicators for the five agro-climatic regions of Australia from current day (2011) to the year 2100 under each of the Representative Concentration Pathways. The scale: 0 was the indicator score in 2011. +1 indicates a maximum positive change and -1, a maximum negative change as at 2100.

The greatest changes in sustainability indicators for the future scenarios 2011 to 2100 are summarised as follows:

- The greatest negative magnitude of change across all scenarios and regions is expected under RCP8.5 (see Appendix 1 for an explanation of the RCP levels);
- The least negative magnitude of change across all scenarios and regions is expected under RCP2.6;
- Under RCP4.5 and 6.0 most regions are expected to experience weak to moderate negative magnitudes of change, although the patterns across regions and indicators are variable;
- The greatest positive magnitude of change across all scenarios is expected under RCP2.6, although the patterns across regions and indicators are variable;
- The Central arid shows an extreme positive magnitude of change across all scenarios for minerals; and
- The South-east temperate shows an extreme positive magnitude of change for RCP2.6 for built capital.

Major Findings (continued)

We will be wise to become more cognisant of the bio-physical limits of our environment and more sensitively negotiate the use of resources within safe working limits. We will need to:

- Invest a lot more time and energy in participating in developing and articulating a set of vision narratives appropriate for the five agro-climatic regions and their communities;
- Work on and promote a narrative of a positive and different future from that which is currently likely; establish a dialogue between regional and national stakeholders concerning decision-making and good governance;
- Retain a greater portion of revenue from non-renewable resources and invest this in infrastructure, people and skills;
- Recognise bio-geographic regional differences and encourage governance and management arrangements that allow more locally applicable adaptations;
- Define the natural limits and the negotiable restrictions within which resources can be used;
- Within these limits, allow greater autonomy for local innovation; and
- Identify those actions that have not been successful to highlight what can be learned.

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science & management?

Management of Australian ecosystems for productivity and conservation is both a public and private responsibility. The expert evaluation of sustainability indicators conducted by this group highlights how different the agro-climatic regions of Australia are, and are likely to be in the future.

The analysis highlights the complexity in achieving desirable futures and it is suggested that this is best managed through decentralised and devolved decision-making at a regional level. The social and economic drivers shaping our landscapes can be reflected by selecting suitable sustainability indicators. The graphical representation of net change in these indicators, although subjective and qualitative, can provide the basis of discussion, debate, decision-making, policy design, and future direction setting by communities and regions. The analysis provides an example of integrating the diverse processes in a regional landscape.

This work also demonstrates the importance of a multi-disciplinary analysis of current and possible future landscapes. It has identified that many of the management interventions aimed at repairing land use degradation have had limited success. It is suggested that community engagement and output expectations are excessively top-down and technology driven most often at the expense of genuine participation. A different approach that develops a regional, shared, values-rich narrative of what people want to experience in their landscape should be developed and used to guide management. Significant improvement in consistent monitoring and measurement would also greatly assist in identifying successful management.

Outcomes and products

Bryan, B., Meyer, W., Campbell, A., Harris, G., Lefroy, T., Lyle, G., Martin, P., McLean, J., Montagu, K., Rickards, L., Summers, D., Thackway, R., Wells, S., Young, M. (2013). The second industrial transformation of Australian landscapes. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 5: 1-10.

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Appendix 1: Description of the four scenarios (Representative Concentration Pathway) after van Vuuren et al. (2011).

Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP)	RCP 2.6 Mitigation, peak and decline	RCP 4.5 Medium-Low stabilisation	RCP 6.0 Medium-high stabilisation	RCP 8.5 Very high baseline emissions
Broad description	Medium development scenario for population, energy and land use. Energy demand grows in emerging economies, energy demand levels off in developed economies, increase in agricultural production driven by increasing population, bioenergy expansion and energy efficiency, technology transfer	Stabilisation scenario – assumes that climate policies are invoked to achieve the goal of limiting emissions and radiative forcing, energy efficiency, forest land expansion.	Climate policy intervention scenario. Global market for emissions permits is implemented although emissions mitigation is low. Population and economic growth drives expansion in urban areas and croplands	Economic disparity between countries, slow economic development, few efficiency gains, high energy demand, limited trade in energy/technology, modest rates of technological progress, emphasis on country-level self-sufficiency, high ongoing fossil fuel use